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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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ENVIRONMENTAL NON GOVERNMENTAL ORGANISATIONS AND THEIR STATUS IN PROTECTING THE ENVIRONMENT

By
Stella.O. Idehen*

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the status of Environmental Non-Governmental Organisations (ENGOS) with respect to protecting the environment from degradation. The study examines the diverse functions carried out by ENGOS such as creating awareness, provision of amenities, filing suits on behalf of communities to arrest degradation of the environment. This paper also examines the historical evolution of Environmental NGOs as well as analyses the issue of locus standi. The paper analyses the courts attitude to the restrictive interpretation of locus standi as well as discusses the position of locus standi in other jurisdictions. In doing so, the study discovers several limitations that hinder NGOs from effectively performing their functions. Doctrinal methodology is utilised by relying on data via case studies, review of court rulings and legal frameworks, internet, materials and library sources to examine the issues discussed herein. A review of locus standi shows that strict interpretation of it hampers public interest litigations and limits NGOs' ability to contribute to social justice. The study finds that one of such limitation has been the strict interpretation of "locus standi". This limitation undermines the ability of NGOs seeking to engage in private litigation. Over the years, research shows that courts in Nigeria interpreted locus standi rigidly and this prevented NGOs and public spirited individuals from filing matters in court as failure to show sufficient interest caused a lot of pain on communities. However, with the case of Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation in 2019, NGOs and individuals can now file cases as a result of the liberal interpretation delivered by the Supreme Court of Nigeria. This study analyses how effective this judgement has aided the role of environmental NGOs in performing their role towards protecting the environment. Recommendations are proffered among which is that courts follow judicial precedence by way of judicial activism and legislative legal reform as it would encourage NGOs to carry out their duties effectively without any obstacles. The study concludes that this would be a welcome development that would help in ensuring a healthy environment as accessibility to justice by all will now be achievable.

KEYWORDS: Environment, Protection, Non-Governmental Organisation, judicial activism, Locus standi

1. INTRODUCTION

Humanity's survival depends on the conservation of nature and the natural resources of the earth in the form of soil, water, atmosphere, and of the forests, plants and life.¹ The massive growth in past decades and presently in world population and lifestyles brought about by economic growth and technology in developed and developing states have greatly increased and led to accelerating degradation and loss of nature, natural resources and biodiversity.² Research shows that if large scale degradation is allowed to continue, whether from natural or human activities, loss of such massive diversity will be irreplaceable.³ Non- governmental Organisations have long been recognized as crucial actors in global environmental politics particularly with their involvement in issues concerning biodiversity, conservation, desertification, trans-boundary air pollution and climate change. However, there are several issues that hinder them from carrying out their functions. These issues range from lack of funding, weak regulatory policies, and the issue of locus standi.

In Nigeria, Environmental NGOs have faced difficulty in accessing courts for prosecution of degradation of the environment and a major issue that is identified is the issue of *locus standi* that has been a source of challenge to environmental NGOs and this has frustrated actions that ought to have been taken by them in protecting the environment. It was a herculean task for ENGOs. However, this issue was resolved in the 2019 case of *Centre for Oil Pollution*. It is hoped that this will serve as an impetus in enabling courts to exercise judicial activism as well as encourage Environmental NGOs to bring more environmental cases to court to ensure protection of the environment. This paper shall discuss the historical evolution of NGOs, the functions of NGOs, and examine the issue of *locus standi* in Nigeria alongside that of foreign jurisdictions and find out how this has helped in this wise, the roles of environmental NGOs.

*Ass. Prof, LL.B.,BL.,LL.M, Ph.D. Benson Idahosa University, Benin City, Edo State, sidehen@biu.edu.ng,08170289130

¹ Birnie, Patricia, Boyle, Alan & Redgwell, Catherine, “*International Law & the Environment*”, (New York; Oxford University Press;2009)p.583

² Ibid

³ Ibid

2. CONCEPTUAL DEFINITIONS

i. Non-Governmental Organisations

Non-governmental organisations⁴ are bodies that have no governmental funding and that have certain objectives. They are voluntary groups who engage in national and global issues with a view to providing solutions to various problems and these problems can be in respect of various issues such as the environment, women, children, health, animals etc. There are various types of NGOs that have different objectives like cancer, women, children focused. For instance, a peculiar feature of environmental NGOs is that they exist to resolve environmental and other issues and are not linked to the interest of its members⁵.

ii. Environment

The environment is defined as the surroundings or conditions in which a person, animal or plant lives or operates.⁶ Another definition states that the environment is the combination of elements whose complex interrelationships make up the settings, the surroundings and the conditions of life of the individual and of society as they are and as they are felt.⁷ Section 37 of the National Environmental Standards Regulation Enforcement Act defines the environment to include water, air, land and all plants, and human beings or animals living therein and the interrelationships which exist amongst them or any of them. This paper states that these definitions recognise the interaction among the various elements of the environment which is based upon the activities of man in his natural habitat and the relationship he has with his immediate environment in terms of the water, air and animals as he depends on them for sustenance.

3. HISTORICAL EVOLUTION OF NGOs

Modern NGOs have existed for over a century, originating with Victorian naturalists and philanthropists and have grown and proliferated in modern times. There are several NGOs with several interests. However, the roots of the modern environmental

⁴ Hereafter referred to as NGOs

⁵ Bell, S & McGillivray, D., "*Environmental Law*," (New York; Oxford University Press; 2006) p.133

⁶ Concise Oxford Dictionary, 11th ed, (Oxford, 2006) p.406

⁷ Council Regulation (EEC) No 1872/84 on Action by the Community Relating to the Environment, OJ L 76 (1984) 1

movement can be traced back to 19th-century efforts in North America to examine the costs of environmental negligence, including the impact of diseases and widespread air and water pollution. It was only after the Second World War that broader public awareness of these issues began to emerge.⁸

Environmental NGOs grew as there became an increased interest in environmental issues and this has been reflected by the dramatic growth in membership of environmental NGOs since the 1970s.⁹ The initial focus was primarily on public health, and nature conservation and has now expanded to cover a wide range of environmental issues local and globally. Their main goals include environmental protection conservation and promoting sustainable practices.

3.1 Functions of NGOs

NGOs play variety of roles in protecting the environment from degradation. Their roles are numerous and are in various forms like creating awareness of the gross degradation of the environment by the activities of multinational oil companies. An example is the Ogoni crisis where an NGO/Community based Organisation MOSOP in coalition with both local and international NGOs brought to the attention of the world, the human rights violations and environmental degradation by Shell in Nigeria.¹⁰

Another role is that of bridging gaps between the government and the people. This is carried out by drawing government's attention to the need to address certain areas left unattended to. For instance, NGOs step in to fill the gaps like providing portable water, schools, health centers, etc.

The creation of awareness and enlightenment on the need to protect the environment is another function that NGOs participate in. Environmental NGOs have played a major role in educating the populace of the effects of pollution in the environment. They go to schools to create awareness on environmental protection.

Environmental NGOs play a major role in lobbying for favourable legislations to protect the environment and canvass for judicial review in respect of obnoxious

⁸ Ibid

⁹ Ibid

¹⁰ Oshionebo, E., "Transitional Corporations, Civil Society and Social Responsibility in Nigeria's Oil and Gas Industry", *African Journal of International and Comparative Law*, (2017) Vol.7, 107-203

legislations that do not augur well for the environment. In *R v HM Inspectorate of Pollution, ex parte Greenpeace* (No.2)¹¹, Greenpeace sought to challenge HMIP's decision to allow nuclear reprocessing at the THOP plant in Cumbria. HMIP challenged the interest of Greenpeace based on *locus standi*. Otton J. held that Greenpeace was an entirely responsible and respected body with a genuine concern for the environment and granted Greenpeace the standing to commence the action.

NGOs also fill gaps where there exists lack of confidence in the government of the day with respect to public regulatory process, especially where government finds it difficult to take a neutral and objective assessment of the environment. In 1996, Civil liberties organization and Human rights watch exposed the gas flaring in Gele Gele community of Edo state. Till date, nothing has been done to put an end to this ugly incident as the flaring has substantially raised the heat level in that community causing them to sweat constantly and dehydrate. Another instance is the Ogoni crisis where both environmental and human rights NGOs protested against the Federal government of Nigeria against the exploration and exploitation of Ogoni land by Shell which led to the killing of Ken Saro Wiwa and others.¹² They also help in promoting sustainable development as well as serve as watch dogs in environmental governance.

In carrying out these functions, Environmental NGOs have encountered limitations in prosecuting cases of pollution and one of the major issue has been one of *Locus standi*.

4. LOCUS STANDI EXAMINED

The term *locus standi* is a latin maxim which refers to the legal right of an individual or group to bring a case before a court or any judicial body.¹³ Black's law dictionary defines *locus standi* as a recognized or identifiable especially legal status, a right to appear in court or before anybody on a given question, a right to be heard.¹⁴ This has been recognized in law courts like in the case of *Adesanya v. President of the Republic of Nigeria*¹⁵ where the court stated that the term means the legal capacity to institute

¹¹ (1994)4ALLER329

¹² Punch Newspapers, "Buhari mulls pardon for Saro -Wiwa,others 26 years after execution", (Lagos:23,October2021), 24/08/24

¹³ Law Pavilion, "Locus standi As an Obstacle to Environmental Justice in Nigeria" <Law Pavilion.com/blog/locus-standi-as-an-obstacle-to-envionmental-justice-in-nigeria> accessed 5/5/24

¹⁴ Blacks Law dictionary, <<https://blacks Law.en-academic.com> accessed > 1/4/24

¹⁵ (1981)2NCLR358

proceedings in a court of law. For a plaintiff to exercise his/her *locus*, it must be shown that his/her civil rights and obligations have been or are likely to be affected. In *F.A.T.B v Ezegebu*,¹⁶ Ayoola JCA, stated that *Locus standi* deals with the rights of a party to sue.

Locus standi is also defined as the existence of a right of an individual or group of individuals to bring an action before a court of law.¹⁷ For a plaintiff to exercise his/her *locus*, the following requirements must be met:

- i. An individual must show that his/her civil rights and obligations have been or are likely to be affected.
- ii. He/she must show sufficient interest in the case.
- iii. That he would be affected by the action or damage as a result of the action.

4.2 Position of *Locus Standi* in Nigeria

The history of *locus standi* can be traced from the British common law tradition and its application by Nigeria courts show a legacy of the English common law and during the post-independence cases, the Supreme Court followed the English common law which was restrictive.¹⁸ An instance is the case of *Olawoyin v A.G., Northern Region of Nigeria*¹⁹ where the plaintiff filed an action seeking a declarative relief that Part VIII of the Children and Young Person Law 1958 was no longer valid and enforceable as a result of the constitutional provisions of sections 7, 8 and 9 of the sixth Schedule to the 1960 Constitution. The plaintiff also prayed the court to invoke its powers under section 245(1) of the 1960 Constitution and declare Part VIII of the Children and Young Persons Law as null and void, unenforceable and unconstitutional. The Supreme Court in dismissing the case held that the plaintiff had no standing to sue because he failed to show that he had sufficient interest to sue.

The courts as at 1980 in Nigeria had a restrictive interpretation of *locus standi* and had drawn up factors that would entitle one to have *locus standi*. The case of *Ade Adesanya*

¹⁶ (1999)2NWLR149,236

¹⁷ Lex primus, "Locus standi in Nigeria: An Impediment to Justice", <http://lexprimus.com>, < accessed 28/8/23 >

¹⁸ Taofeeq N. Alatisie, "The Future of Standing to Sue in Environment and Climate Change Litigations in Nigeria", *NAUJILJ* 13(1)2022,29

¹⁹ (1961)2SCNLR5 at 10

*v President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria & Anor*²⁰ created a confused state on the issue of *locus standi* as to its application when Justice Mohammed Bello held that:

“it seems to me that upon the construction of the subsection, it is only when the civil rights and obligations of the person who invokes the jurisdiction of the court are in issue for determination that the judicial powers of the court may be invoked. In other words, standing will only be accorded to a plaintiff who shows that his civil rights and obligations have been or are in danger of being violated or adversely affected by the act complained of.”

It should be noted that the essence of *locus standi* is to prevent busy bodies from wasting the time of the court in bringing actions that they do not have a nexus with.

This case had to do with the plaintiff who was a serving Senator, sued the President of Nigeria over the appointment of Justice Ovie-Whiskey as Chairman of the Federal Electoral Commission. However, during the confirmation process in Parliament, the plaintiff had objected to the appointment claiming that it violates the provision of the 1979 Constitution of Nigeria. Notwithstanding the objections of the plaintiff, the appointment was confirmed and this led to instituting an action at the trial court seeking declarative reliefs that the appointment was unconstitutional. At the trial court, the relief was granted. On appeal to the Court of Appeal, the issue of *locus standi* of the plaintiff was addressed and it was held that the plaintiff had no *locus* having not shown any sufficient interest or that he had an existing right that had been violated. On appeal to the Supreme Court, the appeal was again dismissed and the apex court held that the plaintiff/appellant had no *locus standi*.

The above reasoning arose from interpreting section 6(6)(b) of the 1979 Constitution which states “The judicial powers vested in accordance with the foregoing provisions of this section shall extend to all matters between persons or between government or authority and to any person in Nigeria and to all actions and proceedings relating thereto, for the determination of any question as to the civil rights and obligations of that person”.²¹

²⁰ (n10)(1981)

²¹ This section is in pari materia with section 6(6)(b) of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria as Amended.

The judgment paved way for the misunderstanding that bedeviled several judgments after *Adesanya's* case in restricting a person's right to sue by holding that for a plaintiff to have *locus*, he must show that his civil rights and obligations have been or are likely to be affected.

This position led to the denial of access to justice for many Nigerians and prevented environmental NGOs from applying to court on their behalf or litigating in the interest of the public. In *Oronto Douglas v SPDC & Ors*²², the plaintiff, an environmental activist and native of that community filed a claim against Shell Petroleum Development Company Ltd seeking compliance with environmental impact assessment for a liquefied natural gas project, the Federal High Court refused to hear the plaintiff's matter on the grounds that the plaintiff did not show that he had an interest superior to that of other members of his community to pursue the action.

4.3. Position of Locus Standi in Foreign Jurisdictions

The position in selected jurisdictions was initially one of a restrictive nature in terms of interpreting *locus standi*. For instance, in the United Kingdom, in *Secretary of State for the Environment Ex parte Rose Theatre Trust Company*²³, the court relying on the grounds of *locus standi* rejected the application for judicial review on the grounds that the trust company had no standing to bring the action. Over the years, there has been a liberal approach in interpreting *locus standi* by the courts. In *R v Inspectorate of Pollution, Ex parte Green peace Ltd, (no.2)*²⁴ Otto J. granted green peace, an environmental NGO, *locus standi* in the issue based on the fact that they were an entirely responsible and respected body with genuine and sufficient interest for the environment.

In India, judicial attitude to *locus standi* up until 1980s had been very restrictive where an individual was regarded as a meddlesome interloper and as such would not be allowed to pursue the claim that was before the court.²⁵ However, the situation has changed with the courts exercising judicial activism which allows for a liberal approach

²² FHC/L/CS/573/93

²³ (1990)1ALLER754

²⁴ *Supra*, (n7), p.100

²⁵ Alex Cyril Ekeke "Liberalization of the Rule on Locus Standi before Nigerian Courts: Lessons from India, <Cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-african-law/article/liberalization-of-the-rule-on-the-rule-on-locus-before-nigerian-courts-lessonsfrom-india/3FCIIBF41054A566A4FCDD5AF8148> accessed 22/3/24

to *locus standi* by allowing a broader participation in public interest litigation. In *Maharaj Singh v Uttar Pradesh*, the Supreme court of India held that where there is an offence against public interest, *locus standi* will not impede an individual from pursuing the claim in court.²⁶ In *Mehta v Union of India*²⁷, the Supreme court upheld the right of a citizen to litigate issues relating to the pollution of River Ganges. Through judicial activism, India has abandoned the strict application of *locus standi* and the complex process that impeded access to the courts. It is observed that this liberalization by the courts is the recognition that enables activists and lawyers to pursue public interest cases in India to correct injustices and this has enamoured courts to support them.²⁸

5. STATUS OF NGOs ADVOCACY FOR THE PROTECTION OF THE ENVIRONMENT IN NIGERIA

Earlier on, the functions of NGOs have been outlined and one of the major roles identified has been to adjudicate for and on behalf of a cause which in this instance refers to environmental issues. The status of NGOs as stated are recognized globally and in Nigeria and its recognition was gradual. Access to justice by NGOs particularly environmental NGOs has particularly not been easy in Nigeria in previous years. This difficulty arose because plaintiffs were required to demonstrate that they had a sufficient personal interest in the case, showing that the outcome would directly affect them. The case of *Oronto Douglas* is illustrative here. The standing requirement operates to block access of citizens to forums where abuse of environmental code of conduct could be vindicated on the excuse that such citizens had not sustained direct injury.²⁹ In *Shell Petroleum Development Company Nigeria Limited v Chief Otoko and Ors*³⁰, the plaintiffs / respondents instituted a representative action at the high court in Rivers state, claiming the sum of N499, 855.00 against the appellant as compensation for injurious affection to and deprivation of use of the Andoni Rivers and creeks as a result of the spillage of crude oil. The Court of Appeal held that:

²⁶ 57 AIR(1976)SC 2602 at2609

²⁷ (1988)S.C. 115

²⁸ Alex Cyril Ekeke, (n25)

²⁹ Alatise (n18)

³⁰ (1990)6 NWLR(pt.159) 657

- i) It is essential that the persons who are to be represented and the person(s) representing them should have the same interest in the cause of matter
- ii) Given common interest and a common grievance, a representative suit would be in order if in addition to the relief sought, it is in its nature beneficial to all whom the plaintiff proposes to represent.

The Court rejected the purported representative action and held that the respondents had no standing to sue.

It has been noted that one of the greatest hurdles of environmental litigants, has been meeting the requirements of *locus standi* as plethora of environmental cases abound where cases were not heard for lack of standing³¹. This restrictive viewpoint of *locus standi* limits the role played by NGOs, public spirited individuals and these parties often have the resources and expertise to litigate issues that affect the poor but were denied the right to sue on such issues thereby denying access to justice to the poor.³²

Currently the Supreme Court in Nigeria has through judicial activism paved way for liberal interpretation of *locus standi*. In *Centre For Oil Pollution Watch v N.N.P.C*³³, Plaintiff/appellant, an NGO involved in the function of ensuring reinstatement, restoration and remediation of the environment sued the defendant/respondent at the Federal High Court claiming inter alia: reinstatement, restoration and remediation of the impaired/contaminated environment at Acha autonomous community of Isuikwuato Local Government of Abia State particularly the Ineh and Aku streams which environment was contaminated by the oil spill caused by the respondent's negligence; provision of potable water supply as a substitute to the soiled and contaminated Ineh/Aku streams, which are the only and/or major source of water supply to the community; and provision of medical facilities for evaluation and treatment of the victims of the after negative health effect of the spillage and/or the contaminated streams. In the statement of claim filed by the plaintiffs, the plaintiffs stated that the respondent constructed and laid oil pipelines twenty five years ago, in

³¹ Ibid, see *Amos v Shell BP*(1977(S.C.))18, *Seismograph service v Ogbeni* (1976)4S.C.85, *Oronto Douglas v Shell &Ors* Unreported suit No. FHC/CS/573/93, Delivered on 17February1997

³² Alex Cyril Ekeke (n28)

³³ (2019)5NWLR(Pt. 1666)518

the affected communities for oil mining and production which had outlived their usefulness, which resultant effect of sea water and other factors, had started emitting strange oily substances (hydrocarbon) and other toxic substances that are harmful to the people of the affected areas, causing serious environmental pollution and harm to the people of the affected areas. This assertion was countered and denied by the defendants in their statement of defence and they filed an application requesting that the trial be set for hearing the point of law raised in its defence which challenged the *locus standi* of the appellant to institute the case. The trial Court held that the appellant lacked the *locus standi* to sue and struck out the case. On appeal to the Court of Appeal, The Court upheld the judgement of the trial court and dismissed the appeal based on lack of *locus standi*.

On further appeal to the Supreme Court, the Supreme Court invited five amici curiae to address it on the “Extending the scope of *locus standi* in relation to issues on environmental degradation: the case of NGOs”. The Supreme Court also considered the provisions of Article 24 of the African Charter on Peoples and Human Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, sections 20 and 33 of the Constitution and section 17(4) of the Oil Pipelines Act and acknowledged that the courts have in recent times, applied more liberal tests and the trend is away from restrictive and technical approach to questions of *locus standi*.

The Supreme Court also held that English courts have extended the meaning of *locus standi* and the aforementioned determinant principle in appropriate cases where a non-governmental organization has been held to have *locus standi*. The English courts are not alone in this development as other common law jurisdictions have followed that pattern. In India, the Supreme Court, without any statutory enactment, has taken action to address environmental degradation based on the need to deliver justice. Similarly, courts in England, other Commonwealth countries with legal systems akin to Nigeria's, and the United States have adopted a more liberal approach to *locus standi* in public interest litigation. These courts have recognized that outdated technical rules regarding *locus standi* should not be used to prevent individuals or

groups of public-spirited citizens from bringing matters of unlawful conduct, which violate the rule of law, to the court's attention.³⁴

The Supreme Court further stated that the mere fact that a non-governmental organization has interest in environmental protection will not be sufficient, to confer *locus standi* on it. It must still satisfy the court as to the legitimacy of its interest in the subject matter of the litigation. The Supreme Court also held that the issue of environmental protection against degradation has become a contemporary issue. The plaintiff should be encouraged to ensure that actions or omissions by government agencies or multi-national oil companies that tend to pollute the environment are checked. The Supreme Court also stated that other common wealth countries such as England, Australia and India have relaxed their rigidity in the application of the concept of *locus standi* in public interest litigations and Nigeria should follow suit. The Supreme Court as a result unanimously allowed the appeal of the appellant.

This case has undoubtedly removed any obstacles that *locus standi* would hinder one from challenging matters of public interest before the courts. This would indeed encourage a lot of NGOs to be able to perform their role effectively in the prevention of degradation of the environment.

It has also been noted that many cases on merit, over the years have been struck out by the Supreme Court on the ground of strict application of *locus standi*.³⁵

5.1. Examination of Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 2009(FREPR)

The Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 2009 were passed by the then Chief Justice of Nigeria, Justice Idris Legbo Kutigi and was made pursuant to sec. 46(3) of the 1999 Constitution which empowers the Chief Justice to make rules pertaining to the practice and procedure for the enforcement of fundamental human rights in Nigeria. The provisions of the preamble are so pertinent to our discourse and shall be examined presently.

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ M.Y. Danung & Justin Ileka, "The Concept of Locus Standi: A Dogmatic Impediment to Justice or a Flexible Tool of Convenience?", *International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy*, 4(1)2022p.59

Paragraph 3 of the preamble sets out the process for the enforcement of fundamental human rights before Nigerian courts.

Paragraph 3(a) provides for the court to apply and interpret chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution as well as the African Charter and Peoples Rights with the view to advancing and realizing the rights and freedoms contained in them and affording the protections that are intended.

Paragraph 3 (d) urges the court to pursue enhanced access to justice for all classes of litigants, especially the poor, illiterate, uninformed, the vulnerable, the incarcerated and the unrepresented.

Paragraph 3(e) makes provision for the liberal application of the rule of *locus standi* as one of its overriding objectives and states thus:

The court shall encourage and welcome public interest litigation in the human rights field and no human rights case may be dismissed or struck out for want of *locus standi*. In particular human rights activists, advocates or groups as well as any non-governmental organisation may institute human rights application on behalf of any potential applicant. In human rights litigation, the applicant may include the following:

- i. Anyone acting in his own interest
- ii. Anyone acting on behalf of another person
- iii. Any one acting as a member of, or in the interest of a group or class of persons;
- iv. Any one acting in the public interest
- v. Association acting in the interest of its members or other individuals or groups

The Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 2009 was made to address the injustice created by its predecessor the FREPR 1979 and was also made to simplify/ease the procedure for enforcement of fundamental rights in Nigeria.³⁶ It is also noted that the Rule of 2009 was construed to liberalise the strict application of

³⁶ Alex Cyril Ekeke(n27)

the rule of *locus standi* before Nigerian courts only in the respect of public interest litigation in the human rights field.³⁷

Drawing from the above discourse, it can be appreciated that the Supreme Court in *Centre for Oil Pollution's* case has also acknowledged the public interest litigation addressed in the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 2009 when the Supreme Court stated that as long as an action is brought for the benefit of a class or group for public interest, the issue of *locus standi* cannot prevent such action. Therefore, public interest litigants can institute actions without necessarily incurring private injuries.³⁸

It is also submitted that environmental issues relating to pollution, degradation and the like can be interpreted as a violation of right to life as provided for in section 33 of the 1999 Constitution which is a fundamental human right and has according to Justice Eko, JSC, that in order to broadly determine *locus standi*, under environmental rights as human rights, Article 24 of the African Charter on Peoples and Human Rights should be read together with sections 33(1) and 20 of the Constitution on the role of the State in preserving the environment for the health and by extension lives of Nigerians.³⁹

Article 24 of the African Charter and Peoples Rights provides that all people shall have the right to a general satisfactory environment favourable to their development.

Section 33(1) of the 1999 Constitution states every person has a right to life and no one shall be deprived intentionally of his life, save in the execution of a court order in respect of a criminal offence of which he has been found guilty in Nigeria

Section 20 of the 1999 Constitution provides that the State must protect and enhance the environment, safeguarding water, air, land, forests and wildlife.

Mbadugha notes that the decision of the Supreme Court is indeed a landmark decision and a departure from the precedent laid down in previous cases like *Adesanya's* case

³⁷ Ibid

³⁸ Joseph N. Mbadugha, "Environmental Public Interest Litigation in Nigeria: A Case Comment on *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation*", *Unizik Journal of Public and Private Law*, Vol.11, May 2021, p.

³⁹ See paras H-C per Eko JSC, P.597-598

as it not only extended the determinant of *locus standi* but also makes environmental right a human right.⁴⁰

6. RECOGNITION OF ENVIRONMENTAL RIGHTS AS HUMAN RIGHTS

The Supreme Court in addressing the issue of *locus standi* has also recognized Sections 20 and 33 of the 1999 Constitution, Article 24 of the African Charter on Human, and Peoples Rights as well as section 17(4) of the Oil Pipelines Act and established that the right to a healthy environment is a variant of human right in Nigeria as the above provisions establish that the 1999 Constitution, legislature and the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights which has been domesticated and is now part of our municipal laws together recognize the fundamental rights of the citizenry to a clean and healthy environment and the elevation of environmental matters to human right is seen as a welcome development.⁴¹ It is the view of this paper that as much as *locus standi* has been liberalized in terms of public interest litigation, further reforms be taken to allow NGOs participate in environmental litigation when there is pollution on behalf of individuals and this should be devoid of strict requirements as long as evidence is shown that pollution has occurred.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

To ensure that NGOs are able to implement their roles effectively, this paper recommends:

1. That an awareness campaign on public interest litigation be made to educate the public on the role and status of non-governmental organisations in accessing the courts for justice with respect to protection of the environment.
2. That an enabling environment be created where courts would follow judicial precedents with respect to the decision in *Centre for Oil Pollution* case.
3. That legal frameworks be created to enable environmental NGOs to act as watchdogs to ensure compliance with environmental protection.

8. CONCLUSION

⁴⁰ Joseph Mbadugha, (n38)p.60

⁴¹ Ibid

An examination has been made of the role that NGOs play in the protection of the environment and the issue of *locus standi*. It is important to state that the case of *Centre for Oil Pollution* has changed the narrative with respect to protection of the environment. This will go a long way in encouraging NGOs and public-spirited individuals who have the interest of the citizenry to bring action to court against anyone who degrades the environment. It will also ensure that governments and its agencies shall be upstanding and accountable to the people as NGOs will act as watchdogs where frameworks are enacted to enable them be very effective in carrying out their role in protecting the environment.